

The structure (I) has been further confirmed from the results of periodate oxidation. Upon oxidation with sodium metaperiodate, the polysaccharide consumed 1.03 moles of oxidant with committant liberation of 0.28 moles of formic acid per mole of anhydro hexose unit. On Smith degradation the periodate oxidised polysaccharide furnished galactose, glycerol erythritol, which are present in a molar ratio of 1:1.02:2.24 moles respectively. The periodate oxidation results were found to be in good agreement with the structure (I) of the repeating unit of the polysaccharide.

As reported earlier the molecular weight of *C. grandis* seed polysaccharide was found to be in the order of 9.2×10^5 . Since structure (I) consists of 12 anhydro hexose residues only, it becomes obvious that five such repeating units are present in the full structure (II) of *C. grandis* seed polysaccharide.

II

Experimental

Unless otherwise stated, all evaporations were carried out at 40-50° under diminished pressure. Specific rotations are equilibrium values and melting points are uncorrected. Paper chromatographic analyses were carried with following solvent system (V/V) : (S₁) n-Butanol-Ethanol-Water (4 : 1 : 5, upper layer)⁶, (S₂) Ethyl acetate-Acetic acid-Water (9:2:2)⁷ (S₃) Benzene-Ethanol-Water (167 : 47 : 15)⁸. The following spray reagents were used for detecting the sugars (R₁) Acetone silver nitrate-Alcoholic sodium hydroxide⁹, (R₂) p-Anisidine phosphate¹⁰, (R₃) Sodium metaperiodate-Benzidine B¹¹. The anilide derivative of methylated sugar was prepared by refluxing an ethanolic solution of sugar with freshly distilled aniline for 1 hr on a steam bath.

Methylation of the polysaccharide—Purified polysaccharide (8g) was dissolved in water and the resulting solution sodium hydroxide (30% W/V, 170 ml) and dimethyl sulphate (75 ml) were added in small quantities during a period 6 hr with constant stirring at 5° in an atmosphere of nitrogen. After treating the reaction mixture with four more lots of the reagent as described above, the resultant product was heated carefully on a steam bath for 2 hr to decompose the excess of dimethyl sulphate. The solution was filtered and neutralized with cold sulphuric acid. The precipitated sodium sulphate was filtered and the aqueous filtrate was extracted with chloroform in a liquid-liquid extrac-

tor. The solvent layer was worked up to yield a glassy mass (2.56 g). The partly methylated compound was methylated by Hakomari method. The compound was dissolved in distilled dimethyl sulphoxide (100 ml) by stirring in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen for 4 hr. Sodium hydride (3g) was added to the solution in small portions during the period of 2.5 hr and the contents were stirred at room temperature for further 4 hr. till the evolution of hydrogen gas ceased. Methyl iodide (10 ml) was added dropwise to the reaction mixture in a period of 1 hr and the stirring was continued for 10 hr more. Five further additions of sodium hydride (2g in 20 ml dimethyl sulphoxide) and methyl iodide (5 ml) were made on successive days. Chloroform (500 ml) was then added to extract the reaction mixture, a drop of which gave neutral test when added to water and spotted on a pH paper. The chloroform solution was filtered to remove precipitated sodium iodide and the

filtrate was washed thoroughly with water. The solvent layer was concentrated (25 ml). This was dialyzed against running distilled water for 48 hr to remove dimethyl sulphoxide and inorganic ions. The dialyzed solution was concentrated (50 ml) and extracted with chloroform. The solvent layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated under high vacuum to yield a glassy mass, $(\alpha)_D^{25} + 24.12^\circ$ (C, 0.207 g in chloroform) (yield 1.76 g, Found : OMe, 43.32, calcd for structure (I) OMe, 45.15%). The product did not show any hydroxyl absorption band in the I.R. spectrum.

Hydrolysis of the methylated polysaccharide—Fully methylated polysaccharide (1.65 g) was shaken with sulphuric acid (72%, 30 ml) and kept at 0°C for 1 hr. and then heated on a boiling water-bath for 5 hr. after proper dilutions to bring down the acid concentration to 12%. The hydrolyzate was neutralised (barium carbonate), filtered and finally concentrated to a syrup consisting of a mixture of neutral methylated sugars.

Characterization and estimation of neutral methylated sugars—Resolution of the neutral methylated sugar mixture was first attempted on a cellulose column followed by elution with Petroleum ether (80-100°)-n-butanol (7:3) and petroleum ether (80-100°)-n-butanol (1:1) successively but no homogeneous fraction could be obtained. Preparative partition chromatographic technique on Whatman No. 3MM filter paper sheets

with solvent S_1 was next adopted for the resolution of the mixture of neutral methylated sugars. Paper strips corresponding to individual sugar were eluted with water. This furnished methylated sugar fractions (1-5) which were characterised and estimated.

Fraction 1—Syrup (0.145 g) on paper chromatography (Solvent S_1) gave a single spot (R_f 0.96), (α)_D²⁰ + 2.07° (C, 0.182 g in water) (Found: -O-Me, 51.9; Tetra-O-methyl-D-mannose requires: -O-Me, 52.5%). The sugar was identified as 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-O-methyl-D-mannose by conversion into 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-O-methyl-N-phenyl-D-mannosylamine, m.p. 141°.

Fraction 2—Syrup (0.08 g), (α)_D²⁰ + 118° (C, 0.136 g in water) was paper chromatographically in distinguishable (R_f 0.892 in solvent S_1) from an authentic sample of 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra O-methyl-D-galactose. Finally the compound was characterized through its crystalline anilide derivative, m. p. 190°.

Fraction 3—Paper chromatography of the syrup (0.222 g) (α)_D²⁰ + 6.3° (C, 0.186 g in water), showed a single spot (R_f 0.81 in solvent S_1) (Found: -O-Me 41.3; Tri-O-methyl-D-mannose requires: -O-Me 41.9%). It was characterized as 2, 3, 6-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose by conversion into its anilide derivative, m.p. 125°.

Fraction 4—Syrup (0.249 g), (α)_D²⁰ + 80° (C, 0.226 g in water had the same mobility (R_f 0.72 in solvent S_1) on paper chromatogram as 2, 3, 6-tri-O-methyl-D-galactose (Found: O-Me 41.9; Calcd. for Tri-O-methyl-D-galactose: O-Me, 41.9%). Finally the compound was characterised by preparing its anilide derivative, m.p. 178°).

Fraction 5—Syrup (0.2319 g), on paper chromatography gave single spot (R_f 0.46 in solvent S_1); (α)_D²⁰ + 98° (C, 0.185g in water) (Found: -O-Me, 29.3; calcd for Di-O-methyl-D-galactose: -O-Me, 29.8%). The sugar was characterised as 2, 6-di-O-methyl-D-galactose by conversion into 2, 6-di-O-methyl-N-phenyl-D-galactosylamine, m.p. 120°.

A quantitative estimation of methylated sugar by separating them on Whatman No. 3 MM filter paper sheets (solvent S_1) followed by the oxidation with alkaline hypoiodide reagent^{1,2} showed that 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5, were present in the ratio of 2:1:3:3:3.

Periodate Oxidation and Smith Degradation of the Polysaccharide—To a solution of the polysaccharide (0.561 g in 100 ml water), an aqueous solution of sodium metaperiodate (0.30 M, 20 ml) was added and the volume of the mixture was made upto 250 ml. The solution was kept in dark at room temperature, for a period of eleven days and the periodate consumption and liberated formic acid were estimated at different time intervals. After completion of the

experiment the consumption of periodate and the amount of formic acid liberated was found to be 1.03 moles and 0.28 moles per mole of anhydrohexose unit respectively.

The remaining periodate oxidised product was treated with ethylene glycol (3 ml) to decompose excess of periodate. The resulting solution was reduced by stirring with sodium borohydride (1.56 g) for 24 hr. After removal of excess of borohydride by addition of aqueous acetic acid (1:1, 5 ml), the resulting solution was evaporated to dryness. The residue was distilled with methanol repeatedly to remove borate ions as methyl borate. The borate free reduction product was dialysed against running water for 48 hr to remove inorganic ions. The dialysed solution was concentrated to a thin syrup which was hydrolysed with sulphuric acid (10 ml, N) for 8 hr. It was neutralised, filtered and concentrated to syrup. Paper chromatographic examination (solvent S_1 and spray reagent R_2) of syrup, revealed three spots corresponding to galactose, glycerol and erythritol. They were found to be present in the ratio of 1 : 1.02 : 2.24.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. N.A. Ramaiah, Director of the Institute, for his kind interest in this investigation. One of the authors (H.C.S.) is thankful to the Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation Government of India, for the award of a scholarship during the tenure of this work.

References

1. S. BOSE and H. C. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.* 1978, 16B, 966.
2. W. N. HAWORTH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 8
3. S. HAKOMARI, *J. Biochem. (TOKYO)*, 1964, 55, 205
4. E. PERCEIVAL, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1917, 17, 121
5. C. I. BISHOP, F. P. COOPER and F. BLANK, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1965, 43, 30
6. E. L. HIRST and J. K. N. JONES, *Disc., Faraday, Soc.*, 1949, 1, 268
7. M. BISWAS and S. BOSE, *Sci. & Cult.*, 1966, 32, 134
8. S. M. PATRIDGE and R. C. WESTALL, *Biochem. J.*, 1948, 42, 238.
9. P. ANDREWS, L. HOUGH and J. K. N. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1188
10. W. E. TREVELYAN, D. P. PROCTOR and J. S. MORRISON, *Nature*, 1950, 166, 444
11. S. MUKHERJEE and H. C. SRIVASTAVA, *Nature*, 1952, 169, 320
12. L. HOUGH, J. K. N. JONES and W. H. WADMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1702
13. S. K. CHANDA, E. L. HIRST, J. K. N. JONES and E. PERCEIVAL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1289